

NIOSOMES: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF STRUCTURE, PREPARATION AND APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

Niosomes are a novel drug delivery system that are finding application in drug targeting antineoplastic treatment, leishmaniasis treatment, delivery of peptide drugs, transdermal drug delivery systems, cosmetics, immunological application of peptide drugs, carriers for haemoglobin, sustained release etc. A niosome is a non-ionic surfactant based liposomes. It is formed by cholesterol with the use of other excipients. The various methods used in the formation of niosomes such as ether injection method, sonication, microfluidization, hand shaking method for the different types of niosomes. The goal of this article focuses on the recent advances in niosomal drug delivery, potential advantages over other delivery systems, formulation methods, methods of characterization, limitation of niosomes, comparison of niosomes v/s liposomes, application of niosomes, marketed products of

niosomes and the current research in the field of niosomes.

KEYWORDS: Niosome, Novel Drug Delivery, Method.

INTRODUCTION

The skin that covers throughout the body serves as a platform for drug delivery, but the stratum corneum the outer layer act as an obstacle for the delivery of drug through the skin.^[1] Several technologies was developed to bypass or modulate this barrier, thereby delivers definite amount of drug at a defined rate to the dermal microcirculation; which includes physical, chemical and carrier approaches.^[2] Thereby, making it a more prominent carrier

than the oral delivery as it circumvents the variables that influence gastrointestinal absorption, overcome the hepatic metabolism and delivers the drug at controlled and constant rate thereby reducing the side effects.^[3] Colloidal carrier have distinct advantages over conventional drug delivery as it act as drug containing reservoirs, modification of the particle composition or surface can adjust the release rate to the target site. Even though, these carriers produce some problem with the industrial production and clinical application, are likely to play an increasingly important role in drug delivery.^[4,5] Among the various colloid carriers, liposome and niosomes can encapsulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. The hydrophilic drug is encapsulated inside the vesicles whereas the lipophilic drug is partitioned between the hydrophilic domains. Liposomes are produced by the self-assembly of phospholipids in aqueous phase to form bilayer which may be spherical unilamellar or multilamellar vesicles. They were considered to as an efficient carrier to transdermal drug delivery as it can loosen the stratum corneum and hence help in the penetration of drug. Though they produce potent action in pharmaceuticals as drug delivery, still produces significant problems. That is, liposome may undergo some problems like degradation by hydrolysis in aqueous solution, sedimentation and aggregation on storage and cannot sterilize for clinical use. Still, chemical instability like oxidation of phospholipids was not avoided. These pave the way to the discovery of non-ionic surfactant vesicles known as niosomes. Niosomes first reported in the seventies in the field of cosmetics and now used in drug targeting. In both these colloidal carrier, phospholipids and non-ionic surfactant used act as penetration enhancer and hence can overcome the barrier of transdermal drug delivery. Although the niosomes, overcame the problem associated with chemical stability on storage, has some physical problems like aggregation, fusion, leakage of drug from the vesicles and hydrolysis of drug on storage were produced.^[6]

Non-ionic surfactant vesicles or niosomes whose structure and properties are similar to liposomes have been developed. Niosomes are microscopic lamellar structures formed on admixture of non-ionic surfactant of the alkyl or dialkyl polyglycerol ether and cholesterol with subsequent hydration in aqueous media and are capable of entrapping hydrophilic and hydrophobic solutes.^[7,8] Technically, niosomes are promising drug carriers because they possess greater stability, less purity variability, and lower cost. Niosomes also have the advantages of simple method of production for the routine laboratory use and the possibility of large scale production, when needed.^[9,10]

Niosomes are a novel drug delivery system, in which the medication is encapsulated in a vesicle. The vesicle is composed of a bilayer of non-ionic surface active agents and hence the name niosomes. The niosomes are very small, and microscopic in size. Their size lies in the nanometric scale. Although structurally similar to liposomes, they offer several advantages over them. Niosomes have recently been shown to greatly increase transdermal drug delivery and also can be used in targeted drug delivery, and thus increased study in these structures can provide new methods for drug delivery.

Niosomes are non-ionic surfactant vesicles obtained on hydration of synthetic nonionic surfactants, with or without incorporation of cholesterol or other lipids. They are vesicular systems similar to liposomes that can be used as carriers of amphiphilic and lipophilic drugs. Niosomes are promising vehicle for drug delivery and being non-ionic, it is less toxic and improves the therapeutic index of drug by restricting its action to target cells.^[11,12]

Fig. 1: structure of niosomes.

Niosomes are spherical and consist of microscopic lamellar (unilamellar or multilamellar) structures. The bilayer is formed by nonionic surfactants, with or without cholesterol and a charge inducer. Different types of surfactants at variable combinations and molar ratios are used to form niosomes. Examples of surfactants include alkyl ethers, alkyl glyceryl ethers, sorbitan fatty acid esters, and polyoxyethylene fatty acid esters. Addition of cholesterol maintains the rigidity of the bilayer, resulting in less leaky niosomes. Meanwhile, charge inducers provide charge to the vesicles and increase vesicle size, increasing drug entrapment efficiency. Negative charge inducers, including dicetyl phosphate, dihexadecyl phosphate,

and lipoamino acid, and positive charge inducers, including stearylamine and cetylpyridinium chloride, help to stabilize the vesicles. Nonionic surfactants in niosomes tend to orient themselves in such a way that hydrophilic end faces outward (toward the aqueous phase), whereas the hydrophobic end faces inward to each other to form a closed bilayer structure, which encloses solutes in an aqueous solution. As a result, the closed bilayer structure of niosomes has hydrophilic inner and outer surfaces, with a sandwiched lipophilic area in between. To form the closed bilayer structure, energy such as heat or physical agitation is required. Various forces inside the vesicles were found to play an important role in maintaining the vesicular structure, for example, van der Waals and repulsive forces that exist among the surfactant molecules. Varying the vesicle's components (including type, composition, and concentration), size, surface charge, or volume will likely modify the properties of resultant niosomes. Niosomes can be categorized into 3 groups based on their vesicle size, namely, small unilamellar vesicles (0.025–0.05 μm), multilamellar vesicles ($>0.05 \mu\text{m}$), and large unilamellar vesicles ($>0.10 \mu\text{m}$).^[13]

COMPONENTS OF NIOSOMES

The main components of niosomes are nonionic surfactants, hydration medium and lipids such as cholesterol. The self-assembly of nonionic surfactants in aqueous media results in closed bilayer structures. A high interfacial tension between water and the hydrophobic tails of the amphiphile causes them to associate. The steric and hydrophilic repulsion between the head groups of nonionic surfactant ensure that hydrophilic termini point outwards and are in contact with water. The assembly into closed bilayers usually requires some input of energy such as mechanical or heat. Niosomes can be categorized in three groups according to their sizes and bilayers. Small unilamellar vesicles (SUV) (10–100 nm), large unilamellar vesicles (LUV) (100–3000 nm), and multilamellar vesicles (MLV) where more than one bilayer is present.

Nonionic Surfactants

Nonionic surfactants are a class of surfactants, which have no charged groups in their hydrophilic heads. They are more stable and biocompatible and less toxic compared to their anionic, amphoteric, or cationic counterparts.^[14] Therefore they are preferred for formation of stable niosome for *in vitro* and *in vivo* applications. Nonionic surfactants are amphiphilic molecules that comprise two different regions: one of them is hydrophilic (water-soluble) and the other one is hydrophobic (organic-soluble). Alkyl ethers, alkyl esters, alkyl amides, fatty

acids are the main nonionic surfactant classes used for niosome production. The hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) and critical packing parameter (CPP) values play a critical role in the selection of surfactant molecules for niosome preparation.

Hydrophilic-Lipophilic Balance (HLB)

HLB is a dimensionless parameter, which is the indication of the solubility of the surfactant molecule. The HLB value describes the balance between the hydrophilic portion to the lipophilic portion of the nonionic surfactant. The HLB range is from 0 to 20 for nonionic surfactants. The lower HLB refers to more lipophilic surfactant and the higher HLB to more hydrophilic surfactant. Surfactants with a HLB between 4 and 8 can be used for preparation of vesicle.^[15] Hydrophilic surfactants with a HLB value ranging from 14 to 17 are not suitable to form a bilayer membrane due to their high aqueous solubility.^[16] However with the addition of an optimum level of cholesterol, niosomes are indeed formed from polysorbate 80 (HLB value = 15) and Tween 20 (HLB value = 16.7).^[17,18] Tween 20 forms stable niosome in the presence of equimolar cholesterol concentration. The interaction occurs between the hydrophobic part of the amphiphile next to head group and the 3-OH group of cholesterol at an equimolar ratio and this interaction could explain the effect of cholesterol on the formation and hydration behavior of Tween 20 niosomal membranes.^[9,20]

Drug entrapment efficiency of the niosomes is also affected by HLB value of surfactant. Shahiwala et al. have incorporated nimesulide into niosomes using lipid film hydration technique by changing the HLB. They found that as the HLB value of surfactant decreases from 8.6 to 1.7, entrapment efficiency decreases.^[9,22]

Critical Packing Parameter (CPP)

During the niosomal preparation, the geometry of the vesicle depends upon the critical packing parameter. On the basis of the CPP of a surfactant, the shape of nanostructures formed by self-assembly of amphiphilic molecules can be predicted. Critical packing parameter depends on the symmetry of the surfactant and can be defined using following equation.^[24,25]

$$CPP = \underline{v} / l_c * a_o$$

Where v is hydrophobic group volume, l_c is the critical hydrophobic group length, and a_o is the area of hydrophilic head group. If $CPP \leq 1/3$ corresponding, for example, to a bulky head group, small hydrophobic tail spherical micelles may form. Nonspherical micelles may form

if $1/3 \leq CPP \leq 1/2$, and bilayer vesicles can occur if $1/2 \leq CPP \leq 1$. Inverted micelles form if $CPP \geq 1$ when the surfactant is composed of a voluminous tail and a small hydrophobic tail.^[30] CPP could be considered as a tool for realizing, rationalizing, and predicting the self-assembled structure and its morphological transition in amphiphilic solutions.^[26]

Cholesterol

In the bilayer structure of niosomes, cholesterol forms hydrogen bonds with hydrophilic head of a surfactant.^[27] Cholesterol content of niosomes thereby influences the structures of niosomes and physical properties such as entrapment efficiency, long time stability, release of payload, and biostability. Cholesterol improves the rigidity of vesicles and stabilizes niosomes towards destabilizing effects induced by plasma and serum components and decreases the permeability of vesicles for entrapped molecules thus inhibiting leakage.^[28]

Drug entrapment efficiency plays an important role in niosomal formulations and it can be altered by varying the content of cholesterol. Agarwal *et al.* demonstrated that cholesterol improves the stability of enoxacin loaded niosome with increasing cholesterol content, resulting in increases of entrapment efficiency.^[29] The effect of cholesterol on flurbiprofen entrapment was studied by Mokhtar *et al.* and cholesterol was found to have little effect on the flurbiprofen entrapment into Span 20 and Span 80 niosomes. However, a significant increase in entrapment efficiency of flurbiprofen was obtained when 10% of cholesterol was incorporated into niosomes prepared from Span 40 and Span 60 followed by a decrease in encapsulation efficiency of the drug upon further increase in cholesterol content.^[30] According to the reported results, the addition of cholesterol and its amounts needs to be optimized depending on the physical-chemical characteristic of surfactants and loaded drugs.

Charged Molecule

Charged molecules increase the stability of the vesicles by the addition of charged groups to the bilayer of vesicles. They increase surface charge density and thereby prevent vesicles aggregation. Dicetyl phosphate and phosphatidic acid are most used negatively charged molecules for niosome preparation and, similarly, stearylamine and stearyl pyridinium chloride are well-known positively charged molecules used in niosomal preparations. Normally, the charged molecule is added in niosomal formulation in an amount of 2.5–5 mol%. However increasing the amount of charged molecules can inhibit niosome formation.^[30]

METHOD OF PREPARATION

Niosomes are prepared by different methods based on the sizes of the vesicles and their distribution, number of double layers, entrapment efficiency of the aqueous phase and permeability of vesicle membrane.

Preparation of small unilamellar vesicles

Sonication

The aqueous phase containing drug is added to the mixture of surfactant and cholesterol in a scintillation vial.^[31] The mixture is homogenised using a sonic probe at 60°C for 3 minutes.

The vesicles are small and uniform in size.

Fig. 2: Sonication.

Micro fluidisation

Two fluidised streams move forward through precisely defined micro channel and interact at ultra-high velocities within the interaction chamber.^[32] Here, a common gateway is arranged such that the energy supplied to the system remains within the area of niosomes formation. The result is a greater uniformity, smaller size and better reproducibility.

PREPARATION OF MULTILAMELLAR VESICLES

Hand shaking method (Thin film hydration technique)

The mixture vesicles forming ingredients like surfactant and of cholesterol are dissolved in a volatile organic solvent (diethyl ether, chloroform or methanol) in a round bottom flask. The organic solvent is removed at room temperature (20°C) using rotary evaporator leaving a thin layer of solid mixture deposited on the wall of the flask.^[31] The dried surfactant film can be rehydrated with aqueous phase at 0-60°C with gentle agitation. This process forms typical multilamellar niosomes. Thermosensitive niosomes were prepared by Raja Naresh et al by evaporating the organic solvent at 60°C and leaving a thin film of lipid on the wall of rotary

flash evaporator. The aqueous phase containing drug was added slowly with intermittent shaking of flask at room temperature followed by sonication.

Twelve milligram each of span 60 and cholesterol (1:1) ratio were dissolved in ether and the solvent was evaporated at room temperature, using rotary flash evaporator. 10 ml of the aqueous phase containing drug (1.2 mg/ml) was added to this at 7 °C and shaken for about 15 min resulting in good dispersion of the mixture.

Fig. 3: hand shaking method.

Trans-membrane pH gradient (inside acidic) drug uptake process (Remote Loading)

Surfactant and cholesterol are dissolved in chloroform.^[33] The solvent is then evaporated under reduced pressure to obtain a thin film on the wall of the round-bottom flask. The film is hydrated with 300 mM citric acid (pH 4.0) by vortex mixing. The multilamellar vesicles are frozen and thawed three times and later sonicated. To this niosomal suspension, aqueous solution containing 10 mg/ml of drug is added and vortexed. The pH of the sample is then raised to 7.0-7.2 with 1M disodium phosphate. This mixture is later heated at 60°C for 10 minutes to produce the desired multilamellar vesicles.

PREPARATION OF LARGE UNILAMELLAR VESICLES

Reverse phase evaporation technique (REV)

In this method, cholesterol and surfactant are dissolved in a mixture of ether and chloroform.^[34] An aqueous phase containing drug is added to this and the resulting two phases are sonicated at 4-5°C. The clear gel formed is further sonicated after the addition of a small amount of phosphate buffered saline. The organic phase is removed at 40°C under low pressure. The resulting viscous niosome suspension is diluted with phosphate-buffered saline and heated in a water bath at 60°C for 10 min to yield niosomes.

Ether injection method

The ether injection method is essentially based on slow injection of niosomal ingredients in ether through a 14-gauge needle at the rate of approximately 0.25 ml/min into a preheated aqueous phase maintained at 60°C.^[31,35] The probable reason behind the formation of larger unilamellar vesicles is that the slow vapourisation of solvent results in an ether gradient extending towards the interface of aqueous-nonaqueous interface. The former may be responsible for the formation of the bilayer structure. The disadvantages of this method are that a small amount of ether is frequently present in the vesicles suspension and is difficult to remove.

Fig 4: Ether Injection Method.

OTHER METHODS

Formation of Niosomes and Proniosomes

Another method of producing niosomes is to coat a water-soluble carrier such as sorbitol with surfactant. The result of the coating process is a dry formulation. In which each watersoluble particle is covered with a thin film of dry surfactant.^[33,34] This preparation is termed “Proniosomes”. The niosomes are recognized by the addition of aqueous phase at $T > T_m$ and brief agitation.

T=Temperature.

T_m = mean phase transition temperature

Fig. 5: formation of niosomes.

Lipid layer hydration method

Twelve milligram each of span 60 and cholesterol (1:1) were dissolved in chloroform and the solvent was evaporated using rotary flash evaporator. 10 ml of phosphate buffer saline PH7.4 containing drug (1.2 mg/ml) was added to the dried thin film with gentle agitation. The mixture was intermittently mixed on a vortex mixer. Sonic dispersion of the mixture was carried out at 25 °C using probe sonicator set at 200 watts for 1 minute.^[35]

The Bubble Method

It is novel technique for the one step preparation of liposomes and niosomes without the use of organic solvents. The bubbling unit consists of round-bottomed flask with three necks positioned in water bath to control the temperature. Water-cooled reflux and thermometer is positioned in the first and second neck and nitrogen supply through the third neck. Cholesterol and surfactant are dispersed together in this buffer (pH 7.4) at 70°C, the dispersion mixed for 15 seconds with high shear homogenizer and immediately afterwards “bubbled” at 70°C using nitrogen gas.^[36]

Multiple membrane extrusion method

Mixture of surfactant, cholesterol and dicetyl phosphate in chloroform is made into thin film by evaporation. The film is hydrated with aqueous drug solution and the resultant suspension extruded through polycarbonate membranes, which are placed in series for upto 8 passages. It is a good method for controlling niosome size.^[37]

Single pass technique

In some literature also mentioned as multiple membrane extrusion.^[76,77] In this method, a suspension of a lipid-containing drug is passed from a porous device and then through a nozzle. It produces uniform size niosomes, usually in the range of 50–500nm.^[78,79,80]

The Handjani: Vila method

This method involves the mixing of cholesterol and surfactant to the aqueous solution of the drug. The resultant mixture is homogenized using ultracentrifugation or agitation and the temperature of the process is kept controlled.^[81,82,83]

Heating method

Heating method is patented by Mozafari et al.^[84] In this method hydration of surfactant and cholesterol is done separately in a buffer solution. After hydration, to dissolve cholesterol

solution is heated for 1 h at around 120 °C. The temperature of the solution is lowered and to this buffer solution, surfactant and other additives are added, with continuous stirring. During this stage, niosome formation occurs. These niosomes are kept at room temperature for 30 min. Finally, niosomes are stored at 4–5 °C in nitrogen atmosphere.^[85-89]

Freeze and thaw method

By this method frozen and thawed multilamellar vesicles can be produced.^[85] Abdelkader *et al.*^[90] subjected the niosomes prepared using a thin-film hydration technique to freeze and thaw. They took 8 ml of niosomal suspension and subjected it to five cycles of freezing in liquid nitrogen for 1 min and for another 1 min thawed it in a water bath at 60 °C. Bartelds *et al.*^[91] studied the niosomes of varying composition and did a comparative study of niosomes with liposomes. In their study, they found that freeze and thaw cycle shrinks the niosomes prepared using unsaturated surfactants. They also found that the freeze and thaw cycle reduced the entrapment efficiency of niosomes.

Microfluidic hydrodynamic focusing

Lo *et al.*^[92] prepared niosomes of two miscible liquids using microfluidic hydrodynamic focusing by diffusive mixing. The miscible liquids are mixed in microchannels in a rapid and controlled manner. This method produces niosomes which are better in size and size distribution than the niosomes prepared by a conventional method. Different parameters like conditions for the microfluidic mixing, chemical structure of the surfactant, and device material for the microchannel fabrication can affect the assembly of niosomes. They found that an increase in the flow rate ratio decreases diffusive mixing time and produces small size niosomes. If a wider microchannel is used, it will increase diffusive mixing time and hence large size niosome.

Dehydration-rehydration method

Kirby and Gregoriadis (CIII) were the first ones to describe this method in 1984. These vesicles were first prepared by a thin-film hydration technique, and then these vesicles were frozen in liquid nitrogen and then freeze-dried overnight. Powder niosomes were hydrated with phosphate buffer saline (pH – 7.4) at 60 °C.^[85] Abdelkader *et al.* (C) prepared niosomes of naltrexone by this method for ocular delivery. They compared the entrapment efficiency of niosomes formed using different methods. They found that the entrapment efficiency of niosomes formed using reverse-phase evaporation technique has shown the best entrapment efficiency in comparison to the niosomes formed using thin-film hydration technique, freeze

and thaw method and dehydration and rehydration method, whereas the entrapment efficiency of niosomes prepared by dehydration-rehydration method was better than the efficiency of niosomes prepared by thin-film hydration and freeze and thaw method.

Supercritical carbon dioxide fluid

This method was given by Manosroi *et al.*^[94] In this method solvents used are non-inflammable, non-toxic and volatile. Niosomes prepared by this method have the size in the range of 100–440 nm.^[88]

COMPARISION OF NIOSOMES V/S LIPOSOMES

- a) Niosomes are now widely studied as an alternative to liposomes, which exhibit certain disadvantages such as –they are expensive, their ingredients like phospholipids are chemically unstable because of their predisposition to oxidative degradation, they require special storage and handling and purity of natural phospholipids is variable.
- b) Differences in characteristics exist between liposomes and niosomes, especially since niosomes are prepared from uncharged single-chain surfactant and cholesterol whereas liposomes are prepared from double-chain phospholipids (neutral or charged).
- c) Niosomes behave *in-vivo* like liposomes, prolonging the circulation of entrapped drug and altering its organ distribution and metabolic stability. Encapsulation of various anti neoplastic agents in these carrier vesicles has been shown to decrease drug induced toxic side effects, while maintaining, or in some instances, increasing the anti-tumor efficacy. Such vesicular drug carrier systems alter the plasma clearance kinetics, tissue distribution, metabolism and cellular interaction of the drug. They can be expected to target the drug to its desired site of action and/or to control its release.
- d) As with liposomes, the properties of niosomes depends both on the composition of the bilayer and on method of their production. It was observed by Baillie *et al* that the intercalation of cholesterol in the bilayers decreases the entrapment volume during formulation and thus entrapment efficiency. As the concentration of cholesterol increases, entrapment efficiency decreases.^[39,40]

CHARACTERIZATION OF NIOSOMES

The characterization of niosome is essential for the clinical applications. Characterization parameters have a direct impact on the stability of niosomes and a significant effect on their *in vivo* performance. Therefore these parameters such as morphology, size, polydispersity

index (PI), number of lamellae, zeta potential, encapsulation efficiency, and stability must be evaluated.

Size and Morphology

Dynamic light scattering (DLS), scanning electron microscopy (SEM),^[42] transmission electron microscopy (TEM) ([XLIII]), freeze fracture replication-electron microscopy (FF-TEM), and cryotransmission electron microscopy (cryo-TEM) are the most used methods for the determination of niosome sizes and morphology. DLS provides simultaneously cumulative information of particle size and valuable information on the homogeneity of the solution. A single sharp peak in the DLS profile implies existence of a single population of scatterers. The PI is helpful in this respect. It less than 0.3 corresponds to a homogenous population for colloidal systems. The microscopic approaches are generally used to characterize the morphology of the niosomes.^[41]

Zeta potential

Dynamic light scattering (DLS), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), freeze fracture replication-electron microscopy (FFTEM), and cryotransmission electron microscopy (cryo-TEM) are the most used methods for the determination of niosome sizes and morphology. DLS provides simultaneously cumulative information of particle size and valuable information on the homogeneity of the solution. A single sharp peak in the DLS profile implies existence of a single population of scatterers. The PI is helpful in this respect. It less than 0.3 corresponds to a homogenous population for colloidal systems. The microscopic approaches are generally used to characterize the morphology of the niosomes.^[38]

Bilayer Characterization

Bilayer characteristics of niosomes have an importance on drug entrapment efficiency. The number of lamellae can be determined by AFM, NMR, and small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) for multilamellar vesicles.^[18] Membrane rigidity of niosomal formulations can be measured by means of the mobility of fluorescence probe as a function of temperature.^[10] DPH (1,6 diphenyl-1,3,5-hexatriene) is most used fluorescent probe and added to niosomal dispersion. DPH normally exists in hydrophobic region in the bilayer membrane. The microviscosity of niosomal membrane is determined by fluorescence polarization. High fluorescence polarization means high microviscosity of the membrane.^[31] Moreover, the

bilayer thickness can be characterized using the latter method, together with the *in situ* energy-dispersive X-ray diffraction.^{[EDXD].[39]}

Entrapment Efficiency

Entrapment efficiency (EE%) is defined as the portion of the applied drug which is entrapped by the niosomes. Unencapsulated free drug can be removed from the niosomal solution using centrifugation,^[42] dialysis, or gel chromatography. After this step the loaded drug can be released from niosomes by destruction of vesicles. Niosomes can be destroyed with the addition of 0.1% Triton X-100 or methanol to niosomal suspension. The loaded and free drug concentration can be determined by a spectrophotometer or high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).^[44]

Stability

The stability of niosomes can be evaluated by determining mean vesicle size, size distribution, and entrapment efficiency over several month storage periods at different temperatures. During storage the niosomes are sampled at regular intervals of time and the percentage of drug which is retained into the niosomes is analyzed by UV spectroscopy or HPLC methods.^[43,45]

In Vitro Release

One often applied method to study *in vitro* release is based on using of dialysis tubing. A dialysis bag is washed and soaked in distilled water. After 30 mins, the drug loaded niosomal suspension is transferred, into this bag. The bag containing the vesicles is immersed in buffer solution with constant shaking at 25°C or 37°C. At specific time intervals, samples were removed from the outer buffer (release medium) and replaced with the same volume of fresh buffer. The samples are analyzed for the drug content by an appropriate assay method.^[33]

NIOSOMES AS DRUG CARRIERS

Niosomes are very promising carriers for the delivery of numerous pharmacological and diagnostic agents. A number of publications have reported the preparation, characterization, and use of niosomes as drug carriers. Because of their nonionic nature, they offer excellent biocompatibility and low toxicity. The unique structure of niosomes allows the development of effective novel drug delivery systems with ability of loading both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. Hydrophilic drugs and lipophilic drugs are entrapped into the aqueous core and membrane bilayer of niosome respectively.

Anticancer Drug Delivery

The current treatment for cancer is usually chemotherapy. The therapeutic efficacy of many anticancer drugs is limited by their poor penetration into tumor tissue and by their severe side effects on healthy cells. Various attempts have been made to overcome these drawbacks, including the use of niosomes as a novel drug delivery system.

Melanoma

Artemisone is a 10-amino-artemisinin derivative exhibiting antimalarial activity and also possessing antitumor activity. Dwivedi et al. encapsulated artemisone in niosomes using thin-film hydration method. The formulations showed highly selective cytotoxicity towards the melanoma cells with negligible toxicity towards the normal skin cells. 5-Fluorouracil (5FU), largely used in the treatment of different forms of skin cancers, was encapsulated in an innovative bola-niosomal system made up of α,ω -hexadecyl-bis-(1-aza-18-crown-6) (bolasurfactant), Span 80, and cholesterol. The percutaneous permeation of 5-FU-loaded bolaniosomes was evaluated by using human stratum corneum and epidermis membranes. Bolaniosomes provided an increase of the drug penetration of 8- and 4-fold with respect to free drug aqueous solution. The use of cisplatin is limited due to its severe toxic effects. Gude et al. synthesized niosomal cisplatin by using Span 60 and cholesterol and investigated the antimetastatic activity in experimental metastatic model of B16F10 melanoma. Their results suggest that cisplatin encapsulated in niosomes has significant antimetastatic activity and reduced toxicity when compared to free cisplatin.^[46]

Breast Cancer

5-FU-loaded polyethylene glycol- (PEG-) coated and uncoated bola-niosomes were prepared by Cosco et al. and were tested on breast cancer cell lines (MCF-7 and T47D). Both bola-niosome formulations provided an increase in the cytotoxic effect with respect to the free drug. *In vivo* experiments on MCF-7 xenograft tumor SCID mice models showed a more effective antitumor activity of the PEGylated niosomal 5-FU at a concentration ten times lower (8 mg/kg) than that of the free solution of the drug (80 mg/kg) after a treatment of 30 days.^[45] Cantharidin-entrapped niosomes were prepared by injection method. Their potential in enhancing the antitumor activities of the drug and reducing its toxicity was evaluated on human breast cancer cell line MCF-7. Moreover, *in vivo* therapeutic efficacy was investigated in S₁₈₀ tumor-bearing mice. Mice treated with 1.0 mg/kg niosomal cantharidin showed the most effective antitumor activity, with an inhibition rate of 52.76%, which was significantly

higher than that of the same concentration of free cantharidin (1.0 mg/kg, 31.05%).^[46] Recently, tamoxifen citrate niosomes were prepared by film hydration technique for localized cancer therapy through *in vitro* breast cancer cytotoxicity as well as *in vivo* solid antitumor efficacy. The optimized niosomal formulation of tamoxifen showed significantly enhanced cellular uptake (2.8-fold) and exhibited significantly greater cytotoxic activity on MCF-7 breast cancer cell line. *In vivo* experiments showed enhanced tumor volume reduction induced by niosomal tamoxifen when compared to free tamoxifen.^[47]

Ovarian Cancer

Uchegbu *et al.* prepared doxorubicin loaded niosomes. The activity of doxorubicin in hexadecyl diglycerol ether (C₁₆G₂) and Span 60 niosomes was studied against a human ovarian cancer cell line and its doxorubicin resistant subline. According to the results, there was a slight reduction in the IC₅₀ against the resistant cell line when the drug was encapsulated in Span 60 niosomes in comparison to the free drug in solution.^[48]

Lung Cancer

Adriamycin was encapsulated into the niosome using a monoalkyltriglycerol ether by Kerr *et al.* and the activity of niosomal adriamycin compared with free adriamycin solution on human lung tumor cells grown in monolayer and spheroid culture and in tumor xenografted nude mice. The growth delay (i.e., the time taken for the tumor volume to double) was significantly longer for adriamycin (15 days) and niosomal adriamycin (11 days) than for control (5.8 days). It is possible that the therapeutic ratio of adriamycin could be further enhanced by administration in niosomal form.^[39] In another study, pentoxifylline loaded niosomes were prepared by lipid film hydration method. Intravenous administration of niosomal pentoxifylline (6 mg/kg and 10 mg/kg) resulted in significant reduction in lung nodules in an experimental metastatic B16F10 model suggesting accumulation of pentoxifylline in a distant target. Light microscopic observation of histologic sections showed a decrease in number of tumor islands in the lung.^[50]

Targeted Delivery

The efficiency and particularly the specificity of cellular targeting of niosomal drug delivery systems can be further improved by active targeting for tumor therapy, by using a ligand coupled to the surface of niosomes, which could be actively taken up, for example, via a receptor-mediated endocytosis. Niosome surfaces can be conjugated with small molecules and/or macromolecular targeting ligands to enable cell specific targeting. Proteins and

peptides, carbohydrates, aptamers, antibodies, and antibody fragments are the most commonly used molecules that bind specifically to an overexpressed target on the cell surface.^[47-49] Bragagni et al. developed brain targeted niosomal formulation using with the glucose-derivative as a targeting ligand. They formulated niosomal doxorubicin composed of span : cholesterol : solulan : N-palmitoylglucosamine. Preliminary *in vivo* studies in rats showed that intravenous administration of a single dose of the developed targeted-niosomal formulation with respect to the commercial one was able to significantly reduce the hearth accumulation of the drug and to keep it longer in the blood circulation and also to allow the achievement of well detectable doxorubicin brain concentrations.^[20] Moreover, an efficient tumor-targeted niosomal delivery system was designed by Tavano et al. Niosomes were prepared from a mixture of Pluronic L64 surfactant and cholesterol and doxorubicin was entrapped into the niosome. After the preparation, transferrin was conjugated to niosomes surface using EDC (N-[3-(dimethylamino)propyl]-N-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride) chemistry. Doxorubicin-loaded niosome anticancer activity was achieved against MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 tumor cell lines, and a significant reduction in viability in a dose and time related manner was observed.^[51]

Co-drug Delivery

In recent years, nanoparticles have emerged as a promising class of carriers in codelivery of multiple drugs for combination therapy. Combinational therapies enhance therapeutic efficacy and decrease dosage while obtaining equal or greater levels of efficacy and reducing drug resistance. Anticancer drugs often have serious side effects. With multidrug delivery system Pasut et al. achieved higher anticancer activity for carcinoma cells, whereas multidrug delivery system decreased cytotoxicity against endothelial cells and cardiomyocytes, with respect to free drug treatment. In their system, they have developed simultaneous anticancer drug epirubicin and nitric oxide carrying system, in which nitric oxide and epirubicin were covalently conjugated to each terminal of PEG. Nitric oxide acts as not only protecting reagent against anthracycline induced cardiomyopathy but also sensitizer of anticancer drug treatment. In order to increase anticancer efficacy and enhance cardiocyte protecting ability of codelivery system, they used branched PEG as polymer backbone instead of linear one. Multidrug resistance (MDR) of malignant neoplasm is the survival ability of cancer cells under the treatment with structurally and functionally diverse anticancer drugs.^[29] Increased drug efflux is mostly mediated by ATP-driven extrusion pump proteins of the ATP-binding cassette (ABC) superfamily, such as P-glycoprotein (P-gp) encoded by MDR-1, multidrug

resistance (MDR) proteins (MRPs/ABCC) and breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP/ABCG2). These drug efflux pumps noticeably decrease the intracellular concentration of numerous therapeutic agents. Chemosensitizers, such as Verapamil, Elacridar, Tariquidar, and cyclosporine A mainly act as antagonist for P-gp and suppress drug efflux and consequently recover chemosensitivity of MDR cancer cells. Paclitaxel was coencapsulated with cyclosporine A within actively targeted polymeric lipidcore micelles. P-gp inhibition with cyclosporine A caused an enhanced cytotoxicity of paclitaxel. Micelles loaded with this dual cargo demonstrated significantly higher cytotoxicity in the MDCKII-MDR1 cells than micelles loaded with paclitaxel alone.^[50]

Niosomes are promising nanocarriers in multidrug delivery applications^[49] Recently Sharma et al. reported the dual encapsulation of hydrophobic curcumin and hydrophilic doxorubicin in niosomes for cancer multidrug delivery. Results showed that dual-drug loaded niosomes had higher cytotoxicity on HeLa cells when compared to free drugs. In another study, gallic acid, ascorbic acid, curcumin, and quercetin were encapsulated into the niosome as single agents or in combination and the effect of the drugs coencapsulation on the physicochemical properties of the carriers, on their antioxidant properties and capability to release the encapsulated materials, was evaluated.^[60] Furthermore, Marianecchi et al. prepared, characterized, and applied multidrug niosomes using lidocaine and ibuprofen. Results suggest the potential application of niosomes in dermal administration of the two drugs at the same time in the same pharmaceutical formulation, as useful carriers for the treatment of various skin diseases, such as acute and chronic inflammations in presence of pain.^[51]

Antibiotics

Niosomal carriers are also suitable for the delivery of antibiotics and anti-inflammatory agents. These carriers have been used extensively to improve poor skin penetration and as well as enhance skin retention of the drugs. Begum and coworkers designed rifampicin, a broad spectrum antibiotic, encapsulated in a niosomal delivery system. They investigated the activity of this system in *in vitro* conditions and this study showed that niosomal formulation of rifampicin is able to provide consistent and prolonged release of the drug. In another study to increase efficacy of the antibiotics and reduce the dose, Akbari et al. synthesized ciprofloxacin loaded niosomes using different nonionic surfactants and cholesterol in various concentrations by film hydration method. Drug release through bilayers and antibacterial activity of the niosomes were examined. The results showed that cholesterol content and

phase transition temperature of the surfactants influenced the performance of niosomes. Besides, all formulations presented more antibacterial activity as compared to free ciprofloxacin.^[52]

Vesicular systems, niosomes and liposomes, are mostly used in ophthalmic controlled delivery. Abdelbary and El-Gendy examined the feasibility of the niosomes as a carrier for the ophthalmic controlled delivery of gentamicin antibiotic. Various surfactants (Tween 60, Tween 80, or Brij 35) were combined with cholesterol and a negative charge inducer dicetyl phosphate in different molar ratios. The ability of these vesicles to entrap the selected drug was evaluated and the obtained results showed that entrapment efficiency and the release rate of gentamicin is affected by cholesterol content, type of surfactant, and the presence of charge inducer. Gentamicin loaded niosomes composed of Tween 60, cholesterol, and dicetyl phosphate were the most effective in terms of prolongation of *in vitro* drug release.^[51]

Anti-Inflammatory Drugs

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) loaded niosomes have been prepared by several groups. These drugs may cause adverse effects such as mucosal irritation. Topically applied NSAIDs loaded niosomes can substantially improve drug permeation. To investigate the potential application of the niosomes for delivery of anti-inflammatory agents, Marianecci *et al.* synthesized ammonium glycyrrhizinate (AG) loaded niosomes using several surfactants and cholesterol at various concentrations. Drug entrapment efficiency, anisotropy, cytotoxicity and skin tolerability, and some further analysis have been performed for characterization. The AG-loaded niosomes demonstrated no toxicity and good skin tolerability and were able to improve the anti-inflammatory activity in mice. Moreover, an enhancement of the anti-inflammatory activity of the niosome delivered drug was observed on chemically induced skin erythema in humans.^[52]

Antiviral Drugs

Niosomes have also demonstrated the capability to deliver various antiviral agents. Ruckmani and Sankar synthesized zidovudine, which is the first anti-HIV compound approved for clinical use, encapsulated niosomes, and examined their entrapment efficiency and as well as sustainability of release. The niosomes were formulated by combining the proportions of Tween, Span, and cholesterol. Niosomes composed Tween 80 entrapped large amounts of zidovudine and the addition of dicetyl phosphate enhanced drug release for a longer time.⁽¹³⁾ The drug leakage from Tween 80 formulations stored at room temperature was significant

compared to niosomes stored at 4°C for 90 days. Besides, the results of a pharmacokinetic study in rabbits also confirmed that Tween 80 formulations with dicetyl phosphate were cleared from the circulation within five hours.^[32]

Fig. 5: Niosomes As A Drug Carrier.

STRENGTHS AND LIMITATION OF NIOSOMES IN DRUG DELIVERY

One of the most important strengths of niosomes compared with liposomes is their chemical stability. Niosomes are more stable against chemical degradation or oxidation and have long storage time compared to liposomes.^[53] The surfactants which are used for niosomes preparation are biodegradable, biocompatible, and nonimmunogenic. Handling and storage conditions of surfactants do not need any specifications. Moreover composition, size, lamellarity, stability, and surface charge of niosomes can be controlled by the type of preparation method, surfactant, cholesterol content, surface charge additives, and suspension concentration.^[45]

On the other hand niosomes show physical stability problems. During storage of dispersion niosomes are at risk of aggregation, fusion, drug leakage, or hydrolysis of encapsulated drugs. Furthermore the sterilization of niosomes needs much effort. Heat sterilization and

membrane filtration are unsuitable for niosomes. Thus, these areas need further research to produce commercially niosomal preparations.^[53]

STABILITY OF NIOSOMES

The factors affecting the stability of niosomes can be classified into the three categories-

Physical stability

Chemical stability

Stability in biological fluids.

Physical stability

The niosomes can change their physical characteristics in several ways.

- a. The particle size may change because of aggregate formation and fusion. Occurrence of phase separation of bilayer components, upon storage.
- b. Leakage of encapsulated material from niosomes.

The changes in particle upon storage of phosphatidyl choline containing niosomes over pharmaceutically relevant time intervals can be minimized by the selection of proper charge inducing agents. Mostly, negatively charged phospholipids (phosphatidyl glycerol) are used to stabilize the niosomes.

The phase separation may occur when the bilayer composition changes due to chemical degradation reactions or when the bilayer goes through temperature cycles. Sometimes, phase separation occurs *in vivo*, when bilayer components are selectively drawn from the bilayer plasma components. If this effect is undesired, the components that form more rigid bilayers are preferred. In other cases, one might wish to deliberately destabilize the niosomes *in vivo* so that a rapid release of the encapsulated drug is induced. An example of plasma destabilized niosomes is niosomes composed of phosphatidyl ethanolamine and oleic acid. The permeability of bilayers is highly dependent on the physico-chemical properties of the bilayer, drug and the temperature. Three categories of drugs can be discussed-

- Highly hydrophilic, non-bilayer interacting drugs.
- Drugs with some lipophilicity
- Strongly lipophilic drugs.

In category first, the presence of cholesterol in the bilayer of the egg phosphatidyl choline niosomes dramatically reduces the permeability. For gel state bilayers, permeability is low

with or without cholesterol. It is clear that if *in vivo* performance allows 'gel state' bilayers to be used, the shelf life of the niosomes in aqueous media with the proper pH might easily meet industrial demands. In the second category, the drug tends to be difficult to keep entrapped over periods of months as long as outside sink conditions prevail. In the third category, strongly lipophilic drugs have high affinity for the bilayer and therefore these drugs stay there over a long period of time, independently of the state of the bilayer.

As the final remark, the presence of hydrolysis or oxidation reduction products can affect bilayer properties. Although, lysophosphatidyl choline is known to be a lipid bilayer solubilizer, the solubilizing effect of lysophosphatidyl choline in degrading niosomes is neutralized by the simultaneous appearance of fatty acids in the bilayer.^[LV]

Niosomes stored in freeze dried form: The niosomes stored in freeze dried form is preferred for proper *in vivo* performance of niosomes with long term stability. To maintain the particle size distribution after freeze drying-rehydration cycle, a cryoprotectant needs to be added. Different types of cryoprotectants and their possible mechanisms of action have been discussed for niosome stabilization. Usually, sugars are used as cryoprotectant, although other type of excipients also have been reported to exert cryoprotective effects. A number of effects contribute to the cryoprotective action.

- 1) The formation of amorphous glass structures during the freeze drying process may avoid mechanical damage inflicted by ice crystals. It is recommended to store these cakes below the glass transition temperature.
- 2) The sugars may interact with the polar head groups of the phospholipids and stabilize the membranes when the bilayer stabilizing water is removed by sublimation.

Chemical stability

The stability of niosomes depends on the chemical stability of the lipid components and the bilayer components of niosomes, designed for carrying a drug or phospholipids. Usually, hydrolysis and peroxidation are the two degradation process which occurs with phospholipids. The analytical technique to monitor hydrolysis and oxidation reactions are reviewed as under:

Lipid hydrolysis: Grit *et al.*, in 1989 and 1993 have described different variables that influence the hydrolysis reactions of phosphatidyl choline, the major phospholipids, in the most niosomal preparations and the charge inducing phospholipids phosphatidyl glycerol.

Apart from pH, other experimental conditions like temperature, ionic strength, buffer species, and ultra sonication were reported to influence hydrolysis reactions. Many investigators choose the formation of lysophosphatidyl choline as a standard measure for the chemical stability to phospholipids. Since, the presence of lysophosphatidyl choline in lipid bilayer greatly enhances the permeability of niosomes, the most important method for minimizing this problem is the proper sourcing of the phospholipid to be used. They should be essentially free from any lyso-phosphatidyl choline to start with and free of any lipases. Lipid peroxidation: Most of the phospholipid niosomal dispersions contain unsaturated acyl chains as a part of their molecular structures. These chains are vulnerable to oxidative degradation (lipid peroxidation). The peroxidation can occur during preparation, storage or actual use. Peroxidation of phospholipids produces the formation of cyclic peroxides and hydroperoxides. Peroxidation of the phospholipids may be minimized by a number of ways such as:

Minimum use of unsaturated phospholipids. Use of nitrogen or argon to minimize exposure to oxygen. Use of light resistant container Removal of heavy metals (EDTA) Use of antioxidants such as alpha-tocopherol or BHT.

It was reported that niosome of different lipid composition could be steam sterilized without substantial hydrolytic or oxidative degradation.^[LV1]

Stability in biological fluids

The inability of niosomes to retain entrapped substances when incubated in blood or plasma has been known for a decade. The instability of niosomes in plasma appears to be the result of transfer of bilayer lipids to albumin and high density lipoproteins. Both lecithin and cholesterol also exchanges with the membrane of red blood corpuscle. Niosomes are most susceptible to high density lipoprotein attack at their gel to liquid crystalline phase transition temperature. The susceptibility of niosomal phospholipids to lipoprotein and phospholipase attack is strongly dependent on niosome size and type. Generally, multilamellar vesicles are most stable whereas small lamellar vesicles are least stable. The bile salts also destabilize the bilayer membrane structure, thereby, leading to release of the entrapped material.^[50]

FACTORS AFFECTING PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF NIOSOMES

Various factors that affect the physico-chemical properties of niosomes are discussed further.

Choice of surfactants and main additives

A surfactant used for preparation of niosomes must have a hydrophilic head and a hydrophobic tail. The hydrophobic tail may consist of one or two alkyl or perfluoroalkyl groups or, in some cases, a single steroidal group. The ether-type surfactants with single chain alkyl tail is more toxic than corresponding dialkyl ether chain. The ester-type surfactants are chemically less stable than ether-type surfactants and the former is less toxic than the latter due to ester-linked surfactant degraded by esterases to triglycerides and fatty acid *in vivo*. The surfactants with alkyl chain length from C12 to C18 are suitable for preparation of niosome. Span series surfactants having HLB number between 4 and 8 can form vesicles.

The stable niosomes can be prepared with addition of different additives along with surfactants and drugs. The niosomes formed have a number of morphologies and their permeability and stability properties can be altered by manipulating membrane characteristics by different additives. In case of polyhedral niosomes formed from C16G2, the shape of these polyhedral niosomes remains unaffected by adding low amount of *solulan* C24 (cholesteryl poly-24-oxyethylene ether), which prevents aggregation due to development of steric hindrance. In contrast, addition of C16G2:cholesterol:solulan (49:49:2) results in formation of spherical niosomes. The mean size of niosomes is influenced by membrane composition. Addition of cholesterol molecule to niosomal system makes the membrane rigid and reduces leakage of drug from the niosome.^[LVIII]

DIFFERENT TYPES OF NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS

Table 1: Type of Surfactant.

Type of non ionic surfactant	Examples
Fatty alcohol	Cetyl alcohol, stearyl alcohol, cetostearyl alcohol, oleyl alcohol
Ethers	Brij, decyl glucoside, lauryl glucoside, octyl glucoside, triton X-100, nanoxydol-9
Esters	Glyceryl laurate, polysorbates, spans
Block copolymers	Poloxamers

Temperature of hydration

Hydration temperature influences the shape and size of the niosome. For ideal condition, it should be above the gel to liquid phase transition temperature of system. Temperature change in the niosomal system affects assembly of surfactants into vesicles and also induces vesicle shape transformation. A polyhedral vesicle formed by C16G2:solulan C24 (91:9) at 25°C, on

heating, transforms into spherical vesicle at 48°C, but on cooling from 55°C, the vesicle produces a cluster of smaller spherical niosomes at 49°C before changing into polyhedral structures at 35°C. In contrast, the vesicle formed by C16G2:cholesterol:solulan C24 (49:49:2) shows no shape transformation on heating or cooling. Along with the abovementioned factors, the volume of hydration medium and time of hydration of niosomes are also critical factors. Improper selection of these factors may result in the formation of fragile niosomes or creation of drug leakage problems.^[56]

Nature of encapsulated drug

The physico-chemical properties of encapsulated drug influence charge and rigidity of the niosome bilayer. The drug interacts with surfactant head groups and develops the charge that creates mutual repulsion between surfactant bilayers, and hence increases vesicle size.

The aggregation of vesicles is prevented due to the charge development on bilayer.

Table 2: Effect of the nature of drug on the formation of niosomes.

Nature of the drug	Leakage from the vesicles	Stability	Other properties
Hydrophobic drug	Decreased	Increased	Improved trans-dermal delivery
Hydrophilic drug	Increased	Decreased	-
Amphiphilic drug	Decreased	-	Increased encapsulation, altered electrophoretic mobility
macromolecules	Decreased	Increased	-

Factors affecting vesicles size, entrapment efficiency, and release characteristics

Drug Entrapment of drug in niosomes increases vesicle size, probably by interaction of solute with surfactant head groups, increasing the charge and mutual repulsion of the surfactant bilayers, thereby increasing vesicle size. In polyoxyethylene glycol (PEG)-coated vesicles, some drug is entrapped in the long PEG chains, thus reducing the tendency to increase the size. The hydrophilic lipophilic balance of the drug affects the degree of entrapment.^[58]

Amount and type of surfactant

The mean size of niosomes increases proportionally with increase in the hydrophiliclipophilic balance (HLB) of surfactants such as Span 85 (HLB 1.8) to Span 20 (HLB 8.6) because the surface free energy decreases with an increase in hydrophobicity of surfactants. The bilayers of the vesicles are either in the so-called liquid state or in gel state, depending on the

temperature, the type of lipid or surfactant and the presence of other components such as cholesterol. In the gel state, alkyl chains are present in a well ordered structure, and in the liquid state, the structure of the bilayers is more disordered. The surfactants and lipids are characterised by the gel-liquid phase transition temperature (TC). Phase transition temperature (TC) of surfactants also affects entrapment efficiency, ie, Span 60 having higher TC provides better entrapment.

Cholesterol content and charge

Inclusion of cholesterol in niosomes increases its hydrodynamic diameter and entrapment efficiency. In general, the action of cholesterol is twofold. On one hand, cholesterol increases the chain order of liquid state bilayers, and, on the other, it decreases the chain order of gel state bilayers. At a high cholesterol concentration, the gel state is transformed to a liquid-ordered phase. An increase in cholesterol content of the bilayers resulted in a decrease in the release rate of encapsulated material, and therefore an increase in the rigidity of the resulting bilayers. The presence of charge tends to increase the interlamellar distance between successive bilayers in multilamellar vesicle structure and leads to greater overall entrapped volume.^[57]

APPLICATIONS OF NIOSOME

Niosomal drug delivery is potentially applicable to many pharmacological agents for their action against various diseases. Some of their therapeutic applications are discussed below.

1) Targeting of bioactive agents

- a) To reticulo-endothelial system (RES):-**The cells of RES preferentially take up the vesicles. The uptake of niosomes by the cells is also by circulating serum factors known as opsonins, which mark them for clearance. Such localized drug accumulation has, however, been exploited in treatment of animal tumors known to metastasize to the liver and spleen and in parasitic infestation of liver.
- b) To organs other than RES:-**It has been suggested that carrier system can be directed to specific sites in the body by use of antibodies. Immunoglobulins seem to bind quite readily to the lipid surface, thus offering a convenient means for targeting of drug carrier. Many cells possess the intrinsic ability to recognize and bind particular carbohydrate determinants and this can be exploited to direct carriers system to particular cells.

2) Neoplasia

Doxorubicin, the anthracyclic antibiotic with broad spectrum anti tumor activity, shows a dose dependant irreversible cardio toxic effect. Niosomal delivery of this drug to mice bearing S-180 tumor increased their life span and decreased the rate of proliferation of sarcoma. Niosomal entrapment increased the half-life of the drug, prolonged its circulation and altered its metabolism. Intravenous administration of methotrexate entrapped in niosomes to S-180 tumor bearing mice resulted in total regression of tumor and also higher plasma level and slower elimination. Niosomes containing anti-cancer drugs, if suitably designed, will be expected to accumulate within tumors in a similar manner to liposomes.

3) Leishmaniasis

Niosomes can be used for targeting of drug in the treatment of diseases in which the infecting organism resides in the organ of reticulo-endothelial system. Leishmaniasis is such a disease in which parasite invades cells of liver and spleen. The commonly prescribed drugs are antimonials, which are related to arsenic, and at high concentration they damage the heart, liver and kidney. The study of antimony distribution in mice, performed by Hunter *et al* showed high liver level after intravenous administration of the carriers forms of the drug.^[LVIII]

4) Delivery of peptide drugs Yoshida *et al* investigated oral delivery of 9-desglycinamide, 8-arginine vasopressin entrapped in niosomes in an in-vitro intestinal loop model and reported that stability of peptide increased significantly.

5) Immunological application of niosomes Niosomes have been used for studying the nature of the immune response provoked by antigens. Brewer and Alexander have reported niosomes as potent adjuvant in terms of immunological selectivity, low toxicity and greater stability.

6) Niosomes as carriers for Hemoglobin Niosomes can be used as a carrier for hemoglobin. Niosomal suspension shows a visible spectrum superimposable onto that of free hemoglobin. Vesicles are permeable to oxygen and hemoglobin dissociation curve can be modified similarly to non-encapsulated hemoglobin.

7) Transdermal delivery of drugs by niosomes Slow penetration of drug through skin is the major drawback of transdermal route of delivery. An increase in the penetration rate has been achieved by transdermal delivery of drug incorporated in niosomes. Jayraman *et al* has

studied the topical delivery of erythromycin from various formulations including niosomes or hairless mouse.^[59] From the studies, and confocal microscopy, it was seen that non-ionic vesicles could be formulated to target pilosebaceous glands.

8) Other Applications

- a) **Sustained Release:** Sustained release action of niosomes can be applied to drugs with low therapeutic index and low water solubility since those could be maintained in the circulation via niosomal encapsulation
- b) **Localized Drug Action:** Drug delivery through niosomes is one of the approaches to achieve localized drug action, since their size and low penetrability through epithelium and connective tissue keeps the drug localized at the site of administration. Localized drug action results in enhancement of efficacy of potency of the drug and at the same time reduces its systemic toxic effects e.g. Antimonials encapsulated within niosom.⁽⁶⁰⁾

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF NIOSOMAL CARRIER

Niosomes combine several advantages with respect to other nanocarriers:

- Surfactants used to prepare niosomes are biodegradable, biocompatible, and not immunogenic.
- The method used for routine and large-scale production of niosomes does not involve use of unacceptable solvents.
- Due to the chemical stability of their structural composition, the handling and storage of niosomes does not require any special conditions.^[61]
- The physicochemical properties of niosomes, such as their shape, fluidity, and size, can be easily controlled by changing their structural composition and the method of production, Niosomes are able to encapsulate a large amount of material in a small vesicular volume.
- The structure of niosomes protect drug ingredients from heterogeneous factors present both inside and outside the body, so niosomes can be used for the delivery of labile and sensitive drugs.
- Niosomes improve the therapeutic performance of drug molecules by delaying clearance from the circulation and restricting effects to target cells.
- Niosomes can be administered via different routes, such as oral, parenteral, and topical, and using different dosage forms such as powders, suspensions, and semisolids, improving the oral bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs and also enhancing the permeability of drugs through the skin when applied topically.

- The aqueous vehicle-based suspension formulation results in better patient compliance when compared with oily dosage forms; in addition, niosomal dispersion, being aqueous, can be emulsified in a nonaqueous phase to regulate the drug release rate.^[72]
- Niosomes have been reported to achieve better patient adherence and satisfaction and also better effectiveness than conventional oily formulations.

At the same time, niosomes have some disadvantages, which may decrease their shelf life, and include physical and chemical instability, aggregation, fusion of vesicles, and leaking or hydrolysis of the encapsulated drug. Moreover, the methods required for preparation of multilamellar vesicles, such as extrusion or sonication, are time-consuming and may require specialized equipment for processing.^[73]

RECENT ADVANCES IN NIOSOMAL FORMULATIONS FOR TRANSDERMAL DRUG TARGETING

During recent years, transdermal drug delivery from niosomes has been studied in a number of disease models, and current efforts are focused on optimization of procedures, new compositions, and final formulations. For example, new highly flexible niosomes, known as elastic vesicles, have been proposed and are reported to be effective at delivering molecules through the skin, since edge activators (i.e., ethanol) provide vesicles with elastic characteristics, which allow them to penetrate more easily into the deeper layers of the skin. Moreover, the major limitation of niosomes is the liquid nature of the preparation, because when applied they may leak from the application site. This challenge can be overcome by incorporation of niosomes in an adequate vehicle, which can be achieved by adding gelling agents to niosomal dispersions, thereby forming a niosomal gel. Niosomal gels were found to enhance retention of therapeutics by the skin and to provide high and sustained drug concentrations in the skin. A further evolution of niosomes is represented by proniosomes or “dry niosomes”,^[74] which have been proposed as niosomal formulations; these need to be hydrated before use, and hydration results in formation of an aqueous niosomal dispersion. Proniosomes decrease the aggregation, leakage, and fusion problems associated with traditional niosomes and offer a versatile transdermal drug delivery system because, upon application to the skin, they become hydrated with water from the skin under occlusion.

Niosomes containing nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) have been prepared by different groups of researchers. These drugs may cause local mucosal irritation and undergo first-pass metabolism in the liver after oral administration, which leads to partial inactivation.

Thus, only 50% of the drug reaches the circulation. Topical dosage forms are desirable for long-term use of this drug, especially when used to treat rheumatic symptoms.

The efficacy of topical NSAIDs depends greatly on their capacity to penetrate through the skin.^[75]

A novel sustained-release proniosomal system was designed by El-Laithy et al using sugar esters as nonionic surfactants in which proniosomes were converted to niosomes upon hydration of the skin following topical application under occlusive conditions. The vesicles were loaded with vinpocetine, a potent anti-inflammatory agent that might also have a potential role in the treatment of Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease. A number of in vitro parameters were studied, leading to an optimized formula that was assessed clinically for transdermal pharmacokinetics and skin irritation. All formulations prepared showed high entrapment efficiency and all vesicles were in a size range that favored efficient transdermal drug delivery. Taking into account the high efficiency of systemic delivery together with the lack of irritation and excellent safety profile, laurate sugar ester proniosomes could be considered as very promising candidates for enhancing the transdermal absorption and penetration of vinpocetine.

Niosomes loaded with baclofen, a centrally acting muscle relaxant, were prepared to improve the low skin penetration and poor bioavailability of conventional topical formulations containing this drug. Vesicles were prepared by the lipid film hydration method using nonionic surfactant (Span 20) and cholesterol in different molar ratios. Vehiculation of baclofen by niosomal formulations resulted in improved muscle relaxant activity.^[73]

Span 40-based niosomes were used as nanocarriers to improve percutaneous absorption of salidroside, a phenylpropanoid glycoside extracted from the root of *Rhodiola rosea*, known for its pharmacological properties. Enhanced permeation and skin deposition of salidroside were obtained, due to the effects of the excipients used in the preparation of the niosomes. Salidroside-loaded niosomes showed good biocompatibility with skin tissue, immortal human epidermal keratinocytes, and human embryonic skin fibroblasts, and in vitro cellular uptake experiments confirmed that these different types of skin cells had various channels for internalization of the nonionic surfactant vesicles.^[72,73]

CONCLUSION

Recent advancements in the field of scientific research have resulted in the endorsement of small molecules such as proteins and vaccines as a major class of therapeutic agents. These, however, pose numerous drug-associated challenges such as poor bioavailability, suitable route of drug delivery, physical and chemical instability and potentially serious side effects.^[74] Opinions of the usefulness of niosomes in the delivery of proteins and biologicals can be unsubstantiated with a wide scope in encapsulating toxic drugs such as anti-AIDS drugs, anti-cancer drugs, and anti-viral drugs. It provides a promising carrier system in comparison with ionic drug carriers, which are relatively toxic and unsuitable. However, the technology utilised in niosomes is still in its infancy. Hence, researches are going on to develop a suitable technology for large production because it is a promising targeted drug delivery system.^[85]

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